

DEVELOPMENT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN OUR COUNTRY ALONG WITH INTERNET TECHNOLOGY INNOVATIONS

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Abstract The following article provides detailed information about the ways in which the development of information technologies develops this sector and the investments allocated by the Ministry of Innovation and the work done. And the main part of this article is written about the work in the field of development of "Artificial Intelligence", about the history of Artificial Intelligence, and also comments about new experiments made in Artificial Intelligence.

Key words: information, communication, intellect, subject, internet, technology, personnel, standardization

Introduction

It is impossible to develop the field of information technologies and communications without active scientific and innovative activities. It is known that the study of communication and information problems, production of information transmission, processing and protection technologies, creation of intelligent systems is one of the current directions of science and technology development.

"UNICON.UZ" center of the Ministry of Information Technology and Communications Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as a leading organization in the field, conducts research and development in telecommunications, information security, radio communication and electromagnetic flexibility, electronic digital signature and electronic document circulation, and other areas. produces regulatory documents.

In order to develop and improve the normative base of the field, based on the proposals of business entities in the field of communication and information, every

year the Base Organization for Standardization prepares a plan for the production (revision) of normative documents in the field of communication and information. Regulatory documents developed by the center are stored in the automated data bank of regulatory documents in the field of communication and information.

"UNICON.UZ" center pays great attention to the training of scientific personnel. The staff of the center prepared a number of scientific articles that are regularly published in the quarterly magazine "Information Communications: Networks, Technologies, Solutions" and other scientific publications.

Industrial enterprises cannot be developed without active scientific and innovative activities. This is explained by the high scientific level of the field. It is known that the research of informatization problems, the development of information transmission, processing and protection technologies, the creation of intelligent systems are considered to be one of the current directions of the development of science and technology.

Master documents developed by the center Communication and information, stored in the automated database of regulatory documents of the telecommunications sector.

Improving the system of personnel training in the field of information technologies is one of the important conditions for the successful implementation of the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy, the development of digital technologies and the wide implementation of them in the everyday life of the population. Measures taken to increase the efficiency of the system of vocational training and retraining in the field of information technologies create a solid foundation for providing state bodies and network organizations with qualified IT specialists.

In particular, a school specialized in in-depth teaching of information and communication technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorazmi and branches of a number of foreign universities have been launched, and digital technology training centers are being gradually established in districts and cities. . At the same

time, the lack of qualified personnel in the labor market of the republic requires the improvement of educational programs and methods in the field of information technologies, and the strengthening of cooperation between educational institutions and IT companies. To raise information technology training to a new level in terms of quality, to satisfy the demand of the labor market for qualified IT specialists, as well as the strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 "Science, in order to ensure the implementation of the tasks specified in the state program for the implementation of the "Year of Enlightenment and Development of the Digital Economy"

At present, the development of artificial intelligence, which is the need of the hour, has been paid attention to, and major investments are being made for this area by attracting various investors.

In order to expand the use of artificial intelligence technologies, to improve the system of digital data collection, storage and processing, a number of works are currently being carried out in our country to train qualified personnel in this field, to support scientific projects in this direction. .

In turn, the introduction of artificial intelligence into science requires an increase in the number of qualified personnel. After all, experts who are masters of their profession will be the main factor in the penetration of artificial intelligence into all areas. Currently, in our country, the specialty "Digital technologies and artificial intelligence" in this direction has been included in the nomenclature of scientific and scientific-pedagogical specialties of highly qualified personnel, and its passport has been created. A post-higher education institute for "Digital technologies and artificial intelligence" was opened at the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorazmi and the Research Institute for the Development of Digital Technologies and Artificial Intelligence.

A total of 28 targeted quotas were allocated for basic doctoral studies and trainee-research in the field of artificial intelligence. Out of this, 14 admission quotas were allocated for basic doctoral studies and 14 for research trainees. Also,

10 young scientists selected in the field of digital technologies and artificial intelligence will be sent to leading foreign scientific organizations for short-term scientific internships in 2021-2022.

In the framework of supporting scientific and technical research and innovative developments in the field of artificial intelligence, the total cost is 15.1 billion. 9 projects with a duration of 2021-2024 are being implemented.

An international conference on "Artificial intelligence - the basis of technological development" is planned to be held on November 24 of this year as part of the International Week of Innovative Ideas "Innoweek.uz-2021" held annually by the Ministry of Innovative Development.

Artificial intelligence is entering our lives, but it is natural to wonder what it is. Therefore, we bring to your attention some information about artificial intelligence.

Artificial intelligence is neither a format nor a function.

In short, artificial intelligence is a system or technology capable of imitating human behavior in the performance of certain tasks, gradually improving itself using the acquired information. In general, artificial intelligence is neither a format nor a function, but a process that includes data collection, analysis, etc.

When talking about artificial intelligence, it is necessary to analyze its place in business and information technology. The gradual penetration of artificial intelligence into these areas will ensure that the number of artificial intelligence tools increases.

By "artificial intelligence" most people understand the involvement of robots in various fields. But the term artificial intelligence does not mean that robots will replace humans. Its main goal is to expand the limits of human abilities and capabilities. That's why technologies like this are a valuable business resource.

At first, the term "artificial intelligence" was applied to tasks that could only be performed by humans, such as customer service or playing chess. Also, deep learning of computer technology is considered as artificial intelligence. But

customer service, various online games and deep learning of computer technologies are considered a small part of artificial intelligence technologies. It's true that artificial intelligence technologies can help improve productivity by automating tasks that humans perform. However, now its scope is expanding, now with artificial intelligence it is possible to determine the character of people, the abilities of students, the views of the employee towards work.

A look at history

Research in the field of artificial intelligence began in the middle of the last century. English mathematician and cryptographer Alan Turing (1912-1954) is the first author of research in this direction.

In particular, in 1950, an article was published based on questions about the possibilities of technology leaving people behind intellectually. Its author was Alan Turing. Later, the scientist developed the "Turing test" procedure, which is named after him.

Since the publication of the article, new research has been conducted in the field of artificial intelligence. During this period, the scientist, without changing his views, began to express different opinions about machines that do not differ from humans in thinking.

Conclusion

Early work in the field of artificial intelligence

The term "artificial intelligence" was coined by 1956. This summer, a conference on artificial intelligence was held at Dartmouth University in the USA. Scientists such as Claude Shannon (Bell Laboratories), Nathaniel Rochester (IBM), Herbert Simon (Carnegie University), Trenchard Moore (Princeton University), John McCarthy (Dartmouth University), Marvin Minsky (Harvard University) participated in it.

American computer scientist John McCarthy (1927-2011), who gave a speech at this conference, made history as the author of the term "Artificial Intelligence".

The 80s of the 20th century began to be recognized as the discovery of artificial intelligence. Scientists began to develop textbooks in this direction.

Also, in 1997, the famous chess program "Deep Blue" was created, which defeated the world chess champion Garry Kasparov. During these years, a 6th generation computer project based on neural networks was being developed in Japan.

After that, the focus on artificial intelligence increased. From large companies to military institutions began to finance this sector. As a result, the number of new technologies has increased, competition has increased, and artificial intelligence tools have been perfected.

Three reasons for the widespread use of artificial intelligence

Currently, various reasons are given for the introduction of artificial intelligence in the fields, of which we will mention the three most important ones. The first is low-cost high-performance computing resources. The second is the availability of large amounts of data for education. In order for an AI product to make accurate predictions, it must process large amounts of data. This factor led to the creation of various tools, in particular, simple and inexpensive means of data storage and processing, and various algorithms.

Third, artificial intelligence products will strengthen competitiveness. It can offer many tools for companies to reduce costs and risks, expand market access and other beneficial factors. As a result, companies that implement artificial intelligence will be more resistant to competition.

But as in all areas, there are a number of difficulties in introducing this type of innovation. In particular, the lack of qualified personnel and lack of information for its implementation. The reason is that the more data there is, the more predictive artificial intelligence is.

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